

Physico-Chemical Studies of Emulsions : Part V Effect of Time on the Properties and Stability of Emulsions

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Effect of time on the properties and stability of kerosene-in-water emulsions, stabilized with single anionic, cationic or nonionic surfactants, have been studied. The value of viscosity, conductivity, and particle size of emulsions decreases and the value of surface tension and specific gravity increases on aging.

IN the vast majority of commercial emulsions shelf-life or stability on aging is the desideratum. In a smaller, though no less important, number instability is required. In either case, it is desirable to have some method of measuring the shelf-life or stability of the emulsion, under consideration.

In a previous communication¹, temperature effect on the properties and stability of oil-in-water emulsions has been described. In continuation of earlier work²⁻⁵, the present investigations deal with the shelf-life of emulsions of kerosene oil-in-water, stabilized with single anionic, cationic or nonionic surfactants. Properties such as *pH*, particle size, conductivity, specific gravity, surface tension, and viscosity of the emulsions have been determined and the shelf-life or stability on aging has been correlated with the properties of emulsions.

Experimental

Materials : Sodium dibutyl sulphosuccinate (MIB-anionic surfactant), sodium dioctyl sulphosuccinate (MOT-anionic surfactant), cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB-cationic surfactant), cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTMAB-cationic surfactant), and alkyl aryl polyether alcohol (TX100-nonionic surfactant) were B.D.H., England products and polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (T.60-nonionic surfactant) was obtained from Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd., London. In all the experiments double distilled kerosene oil (K.O., b.p. 205° and sp.gr. .7948925 at 30°) and double distilled water (*pH* 6.2 and conductivity $\cdot 85 \times 10^{-6}$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 30°) were used.

Preparation of Emulsions : Emulsions were prepared under following conditions by Agent-in-water method⁶.

- Definite phase-volume ratio.
- Definite concentration of emulsifying agent.

Properties of Emulsions : Emulsion type (O/W or W/O) was determined by the dye solubility

method⁷. Particle size was found out by taking a photomicrograph of the microscopic slide of the emulsion with the help of Carl Zeiss Jena microscope fitted with attachment camera using 15× eye piece and 40× objective⁸.

Viscosity, surface tension, specific gravity, conductivity, and *pH* of the emulsions were determined at 30° by the usual Ostwald viscometer, stalagmometer, pycnometer, conductance meter with "magic eye" and Beckman *pH* meter, respectively, after 0, 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 25, 40, 60, 90, 150, 240 and 365 days, from the date of the preparation of emulsions.

The results are summarised in Tables 1 to 6.

Discussion

It has been observed that there is no change in the properties and stability of O/W emulsions of K.O. for 15 days, that is the shelf-life of the emulsions remains constant, irrespective of the fact whether the emulsions are stabilized with either anionic, cationic or nonionic surfactants. Although afterwards the shelf-life of the emulsions decreases very slowly, however, after a period of one year there is not much change in the stability of emulsions and on the average, the emulsions are found to be fairly stable.

It may be seen from Tables 1-6 that irrespective of the nature of emulsifying agent, surface tension of the emulsions increases with time. There is a fall in the value of viscosity of emulsions on aging. Specific gravity increases and conductivity decreases on aging of the emulsions and there is a very slight decrease in the value of particle size of emulsions with time.

In case of emulsions, stabilized with anionic or nonionic surfactants, *pH* value decreases slowly with time, while there is an increase in the value of *pH* on aging for emulsions stabilized with cationic surfactants and the emulsions remain acidic.

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TABLE 1—EMULSION STABILIZED BY ANIONIC SURFACTANT (MIB)

Emulsion Type O/W; MIB = .05g; K.O. = 10 ml; O/W Ratio = 1 : 2; Temp. = 30°

Time (days)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
0→15	6.70	12.10	7-8	.9137	14.69	51.50
25	6.70	12.05	7-8	.9137	14.67	51.60
40	6.70	11.95	7-8	.9139	14.63	51.71
60	6.65	11.80	7-8	.9141	14.57	51.82
90	6.65	11.60	6-7	.9144	14.49	52.04
150	6.60	11.30	6-7	.9150	14.40	52.38
240	6.55	10.80	6-7	.9157	14.21	52.94
365	6.50	10.00	5-6	.9170	13.92	53.75

TABLE 2—EMULSION STABILIZED BY ANIONIC SURFACTANT (MOT)

Emulsion Type : O/W; MOT = .05g; K.O. = 10 ml; O/W Ratio = 1 : 2; Temp. = 30°

Time (days)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
0→15	6.90	13.80	8-9	.9132	15.90	50.50
25	6.90	13.75	8-9	.9133	15.88	50.60
40	6.90	13.65	8-9	.9134	15.86	50.70
60	6.85	13.50	8-9	.9136	15.83	50.81
90	6.85	13.25	7-8	.9139	15.77	50.92
150	6.80	12.90	7-8	.9144	15.68	51.24
240	6.75	12.30	7-8	.9151	15.53	51.78
365	6.70	11.40	6-7	.9164	15.24	52.56

TABLE 3—EMULSION STABILIZED BY CATIONIC SURFACTANT (CPB)

Emulsion Type : O/W; CPB = .05g; K.O. = 10 ml; O/W Ratio = 1 : 2; Temp. = 30°

Time (days)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
0→15	6.45	14.40	7-8	.9326	11.66	53.60
25	6.45	14.35	7-8	.9327	11.64	53.71
40	6.45	14.25	7-8	.9328	11.60	53.82
60	6.50	14.10	7-8	.9331	11.54	53.94
90	6.50	13.90	6-7	.9336	11.46	54.19
150	6.55	13.50	6-7	.9342	11.37	54.54
240	6.60	12.90	6-7	.9352	11.17	55.15
365	6.65	12.00	5-6	.9366	10.87	56.02

TABLE 4—EMULSION STABILIZED BY CATIONIC SURFACTANT (CTMAB)

Emulsion Type : O/W, CTMAB = .05g., K.O. = 10 ml., O/W Ratio = 1 : 2, Temp. = 30°

Time (days)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
0→15	6.20	15.30	8-9	.9321	12.07	53.05
25	6.20	15.20	8-9	.9322	12.05	53.16
40	6.20	15.10	8-9	.9324	12.03	53.27
60	6.25	14.95	8-9	.9326	11.99	53.39
90	6.25	14.70	7-8	.9330	11.93	53.62
150	6.30	14.40	7-8	.9337	11.86	53.98
240	6.35	13.90	7-8	.9346	11.70	54.57
365	6.40	13.10	6-7	.9361	11.45	55.43

TABLE 5—EMULSION STABILIZED BY NONIONIC SURFACTANT (T-60)

Emulsion Type : O/W, T-60 = .05g, K.O. = 10 ml., O/W Ratio = 1 : 2, Temp. = 30°

Time (days)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
0→15	6.80	1.60	6-7	.9298	11.00	32.83
25	6.80	1.60	6-7	.9299	10.98	32.88
40	6.80	1.60	6-7	.9300	10.96	32.92
60	6.80	1.55	6-7	.9302	10.92	333.01
90	6.75	1.50	5-6	.9306	10.86	3.14
150	6.75	1.45	5-6	.9310	10.79	33.32
240	6.75	1.35	5-6	.9318	10.61	33.63
365	6.70	1.20	4-5	.9332	10.33	34.19

TABLE 6—EMULSION STABILIZED BY NONIONIC SURFACTANT (T \times 100)Emulsion Type : O/W, T \times 100 = .05g., K.O. = 10 ml., O/W Ratio = 1 : 2, Temp. 30°

Time (days)	pH	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity	Viscosity ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Surface Tension (dynes/cm)
0→15	6.65	1.70	7-8	.9294	11.41	32.43
25	6.65	1.70	7-8	.9295	11.39	32.47
40	6.65	1.70	7-8	.9296	11.37	32.51
60	6.65	1.65	7-8	.9297	11.33	32.59
90	6.60	1.60	6-7	.9301	11.27	32.72
150	6.60	1.55	6-7	.9306	11.18	32.94
240	6.60	1.45	6-7	.9314	11.02	33.29
365	6.55	1.30	5-6	.9328	10.72	33.88

The shelf-life of oil-in-water emulsions of K.O. stabilized with anionic, cationic or nonionic surfactants, as a function of emulsifying power of emulsifiers, may be arranged in the following manner :—

- (a) MOT > MIB
- (b) CTMAB > CPB
- (c) TX100 > T.60

It may be concluded that the stability or shelf-life of emulsions decreases very slowly with time and the value of viscosity, conductivity, and particle size decreases and the value of surface tension and specific gravity of emulsions increases on aging, irrespective of the nature of emulsifier.

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